

Dynamic production scheduling for flat steel production

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Summary

Because of globalization the European flat steel industry has come under immense competitive pressure. To retain its market position, costs must be further reduced and unique selling points, such as quality, further expanded. A contribution to these requirements can be provided by an advanced production scheduling in a flexible flow production, without the need for an investment in capital-intensive plant components. Within the RFCS project DynReAct new concepts to improve the flexibility of production scheduling in flat steel production were developed and demonstrated at the tin-plate production site of thyssenkrupp Rasselstein in Andernach providing multiple production steps with free choice of multiple plants for production of a certain product.

The selected concept follows a hybrid scheduling approach combining three planning levels with different planning horizons as well as planning accuracies to provide robust production plans on the one hand and flexible reaction strategies in case of unexpected events or decreasing plant performances on the other hand.

In this work, the concept of multi-objective production scheduling is presented by the necessary foundations for the implementation in a practical use case in the tin plate industry.

Keywords

Multi-objective production scheduling, plant performance models, flexible flow shop, flat steel industry, hybrid approach, Industry4.0

Introduction

In the course of globalization, the competitive pressure on the European flat steel industry is continuously increasing, posing various challenges that need to be overcome in order to retain and, ideally, improve the market position. Digitalization plays a key role in this context and opens up new opportunities. It provides a multitude of technologies to increase production efficiency with cost and resource savings, achieving higher product quality, maximizing plant performance, and

planning a flexible production [1]. On this train of thoughts, efforts to increase data availability and transparency are on the rise, and one of the greatest benefits is to be found in production planning [2] and scheduling based on process data.

Multi-objective production scheduling and plant performance models

A valuable contribution to these requirements can be achieved by an advanced production scheduling in a flexible flow production, without the need for an investment in capital-intensive plant components. Within the EU-funded Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) project DynReAct, a scheduling approach was developed to generate optimized production plans for each individual coil at each production step considering real-time plant information.

This concept enables immediate reactions to critical situations like insufficient plant performance or coils that are outside the quality specifications. The optimal routing and sequencing will be estimated using real-time-capable plant performance models derived from machine learning on large historical data, which will be incorporated in multi-objective optimization methods. This approach enables the associated complexity to be mastered and other factors, such as quality, to be taken into account in scheduling in addition to the classic logistical targets.

The aim of this work is to provide the basis for the implementation of a multi-objective scheduling on a practical use case in the dynamic environment of the flat steel industry. This production scheduling approach was developed based on the use case of a tinplate production at the thyssenkrupp Rasselstein GmbH, which includes the following main production stages:

Pickling: The starting material for the production of packaging steel is hot-rolled steel strip. The scale produced during hot rolling is removed in a continuous pickling line.

Cold rolling: In the cold rolling process, high rolling forces are transmitted to the strip via support and work rolls, bringing the coil to the required thickness.

Degreasing and annealing: During rolling, the thickness of the strip is often reduced by more than 90 percent. The work hardening that occurs must be reversed by a recrystallizing annealing process after the strip has been cleaned of impurities resulting from an upstream degreasing process.

Temper rolling: To give the strip the required forming properties, re-rolling, also known as temper rolling, takes place after annealing.

Finishing: The strip enters a tin-containing electrolyte in the tinning lines, where it is passed as a cathode between two rows of tin anodes. With the aid of the electric current, the tin of the anodes is dissolved and deposited on the strip. By subsequently heating the strip above the tin melting point and quenching in water, the brilliant shine is achieved. Special chromium-plated sheet is also produced in a process similar to tinning.

Since the finishing lines represent the highest complexity of alternative actions in the context of scheduling and offer the largest input of available process data, this production stage was selected as the focus for the plant performance models.

For the present use case, three different promising scheduling approaches were compared with each other. The results demonstrate that each method has its own specific advantages and disadvantages. It turns out that they complement each other excellently instead of competing. Thus, preference for a hybrid solution is the result of this comparison and, in consequence, a planning pyramid (Figure 1) with three different levels has been created [3]:

Figure 1: Planning pyramid

Long-term planning (decomposition approach based on continuous flow model): In this order-less approach for the long-term horizon, the planning problem is simplified to a reasonable level. Hence, a manufacturing system can be approximately represented by a time-continuous or time-discrete dynamic model. The development of a dynamic model of a manufacturing system requires the definition of state (inventory at each production stage) and control variables (production). Besides, the capacity constraints are also considered in this model. The formulated continuous scheduling problem is an optimal control problem with state constraints, and this can then be calculated in a rendering horizontal scheme [4]. Different production routes of the relevant product groups can be taken into account in this mass flow method. At this level, the user can use these options to plan capacities and coordinate the product portfolio to be produced.

Mid-term planning (heuristic approach combining tabu search and travelling salesman problem (TSP)): To solve the mid-term problem in [3] a MOMILP approach combining Multi-Objective Optimization (MOO) techniques with a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formulation was proposed providing optimal solutions for the mid-term planning stage. However, the techniques require high computation time, which is a disadvantage that makes dynamic scheduling for continuous production difficult. Therefore, in order to provide robust and producible solutions for the production planners a new heuristic approach based on the combination of a tabu search algorithm with a TSP solver was implemented providing good order-based solutions in reasonable time.

Short-term planning (auction-based multi-agent approach): The auction-based multi-agent scheduling system is predestined for uncertain scheduling environments regarding resource availability and is characterized by its responsiveness, flexibility and robustness. On a negotiation platform, different agents represent production facilities, the coils to be produced, and auxiliary agents. Thereby, coils can bid on different auction processes at each resource with an available virtual budget depending on their status. Concerning the lowest virtual costs, the utility maximization of each resource agent is balanced with the coil agent's objective. This approach acts towards the user as an adviser and delivers robust reaction strategies based on real-time process data.

This hybrid approach is expected to improve robustness and transparency of the production planning results considering a global production strategy [3].

Key performance indicators (KPIs), which are determined by aggregating information, are used for the overall management of production. They describe the overall performance of production and are focused on decision makers on the management level. If these KPIs were extended to include the ability to consider real-time manufacturing events and data, a holistic description of production performance could be provided from the operator on the line to the plant manager.

In a production with several production stages, each plant pursues its own individual goals, which make their own contribution to maximizing performance. This is due, for example, to the different characteristics of the plants, their respective semi-finished products or the corresponding processing methods. While some of these characteristics are fixed (e.g., construction-related), others are highly dynamic, difficult to specify, or even dependent on the coil to be processed (e.g., selected quality characteristics). As a result of this implied complexity, a deep analysis of historical data was performed to build a robust plant performance model with real-time prediction using supervised as well as unsupervised learning in combination with expert domain knowledge. These predicted plant performance targets are to be processed in the scheduler. The previous selection of targets should be performed with utmost care in the light of the multi-objective optimization problem as well as the curse of dimensionality and the associated combinatorial explosion.

In the final production planning system two real-time plant performance models for the finishing lines were implemented and can be considered on coil-base by the short-time planning system:

Quality Performance Dimension: For the plant performance model regarding quality, the use case of very sensitive products was taken. These materials are packaging materials that are in direct contact with dry foods such as milk powder and require a very bright surface. Small defects in the surface or any contaminants will cause the filling material to stick to the cans and cause quality control to fail. One of the main reasons for this quality problem are spots on the material surface coming from the production process. These products are produced on all tinning lines. In the present use case, the aim is to apply data analysis techniques to automatically identify these relevant spots at an early stage in order to reduce or avoid the associated quality defects via rescheduling. The necessary surface data are supplied by automatic surface inspection systems from the production process. By applying the multi-scale data representation model presented in [5], the positions of surface defects detected during production can be investigated with other product and process information and placed over multiple coils by aggregation. With respect to the online identification of suspect defect distributions, a deep embedding clustering (DEC) [6] developed for industry applications was selected to perform this clustering task and trigger the impulse for appropriate rescheduling strategies in given cases.

Energy Performance Dimension: In the plant performance model for energy, the focus was placed on electrical energy, as this represents the main part of energy consumption at the finishing plants. The individual energy consumptions are collected online across all relevant components of each finishing line and linked to the accompanying material-piece-related production data for exploratory data analysis. This ensures the allocation of energy consumption per coil and order. In a first analysis, the individual features of the production data were examined with respect to their relevance for the variability of energy consumption at the individual finishing plants. Energy consumption over strip length was found to be the basis for measuring this energy dimension. This allows the effects of rescheduling measures or quality problems on this target variable to be recorded. A model based on the random forest approach [7] was developed to predict the energy consumption of a coil on a selected finishing line.

Conclusions

With the scheduling procedure and the plant performance models, the two basic pillars for the implementation of multi-objective production scheduling in the dynamic environment of the flat steel industry were presented using a practical example. On the one hand, the hybrid solution with the planning pyramid and on the other hand the prediction models for the two dimensions quality and energy were discussed.

In the DynReAct project a prototype was implemented able to provide optimize plans for the finishing step in parallel with production. In a successor pilot and demonstration project starting in July 2023 this prototype will be rolled-out to full

production and it is planned to publish a software platform for dynamic production planning in the steel industry and beyond under an open-source license.

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